

Extractive Photometric Determination of Palladium with 2-Methyl-8-Hydroxyquinoline

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Palladium(II) gives an orange yellow precipitate with 2-methyl, 8-hydroxyquinoline in slightly acidic solution. The precipitated complex is extracted quantitatively into chloroform and exhibits maximum absorbance at 425 nm at which wave length Beer's law is obeyed over concentration range of 1 to 10 μg Pd per ml. The colour is stable at least for 36 hours. The stability constant is evaluated and found to be 2.456×10^4 and standard free energy of formation (ΔF°) of the complex to be -8.82 K cal/mole at 27°. The complex can be dried and weighed as Pd(C₁₀H₈NO)₂. The differential thermal analysis, thermogravimetric analysis and magnetic properties of the precipitated complex have been discussed.

LITERATURE survey reveals the use of a number of complexing agents to determine palladium in presence of so many cations and anions. Oximes¹, xanthates², β -diketones and other chelating agents³ came to the forefront in this connection. 8-Hydroxyquinoline has been claimed to be a handy reagent for palladium. The purpose of the present investigation is to use 2-methyl, 8-hydroxyquinoline as a colorimetric reagent to determine palladium by taking the advantage that the reagent forms an orange yellow complex at pH 1-8 which is insoluble in aqueous solution and extractable into chloroform. The chelate in chloroform is having a maximum absorbance at 425 nm at which Beer's law is valid over a concentration range of 1 to 10 μg Pd per ml of the solution. The reagent itself shows insignificant absorbances from 400 nm onwards. The operation may be performed in presence of other diverse ions. Effect of reagent concentration, period of extraction, diverse ions on the extraction behaviour have been tested. The stability constant of the chelate has been evaluated.

Quantitative precipitation occurs at pH 1-5. The precipitate can be dried at $110 \pm 5^\circ$ and weighed as Pd(C₁₀H₈NO)₂. The differential thermal analysis, thermogravimetric analysis and magnetic properties of the precipitated complex have been discussed.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents :

Beckman DU2 Model spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (10 mm path length) was used for optical density measurements. pH-meter (Elect. Corp. of India) was used for pH measurements.

Chloroform (E-Merck) was distilled before use. 0.5% of 2-methyl, 8-hydroxyquinoline (BDH) in

acetone was used as the complexing agent. Palladium chloride stock solution was prepared by dissolving 1 g PdCl₂ (JM) in 1 ml conc. hydrochloric acid and diluted to 20 ml with distilled water. This was standardised by dimethylglyoxime method⁴. Buffer solutions of different pH values were prepared by standard methods: hydrochloric acid-potassium chloride (PH1-2, 5); potassium hydrogenphthalate-hydrochloric acid (3-4); potassium hydrogenphthalate-sodium hydroxide (4.5-5.5); potassium hydrogenphosphate-sodium hydroxide (6-8), borax-hydrochloric acid-sodium hydroxide (9-11).

All other chemicals used were either chemically pure or reagent grade materials unless otherwise mentioned.

Photometric Determination :

An aliquot (1 ml) of palladium chloride test solution containing 188.8 μg Pd was taken in a separating funnel and mixed with adequate amount of buffer solution of desired pH in order to maintain the volume of the aqueous phase at 10 ml throughout the work. Acetonic solution of the reagent (1 ml, 0.5%) was added and kept for 5 min to ensure complete complexation. Foreign ions were added before addition of the buffer to test their interferences. To study the effect of pH different buffer solutions were used. Palladium(II) forms an orange yellow chelate. It was extracted with 10 ml chloroform for 2 min followed by washing of the aqueous phase with 2×5 ml chloroform to avoid loss. The organic layer was transferred, diluted to 25 ml with chloroform and its absorbance was measured at 425 nm and palladium was determined accordingly from a previously prepared calibration curve. The chloroform extract may be shaken with anhydrous sodium sulfate prior to the absorption measurement step in order to remove any retained water droplets.

All the experiments were carried out at 26-30°.

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Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectrum and Effect of pH :

The spectrum of the Pd(II)-2-methyl, 8-hydroxy-quinoline complex in chloroform extracted as above shows maximum absorbance at 425 nm. The reagent itself does not absorb in this range. All the optical density measurements were carried out at 425 nm. Study of extraction behaviour of Pd(II) over the pH range 1 to 11 shows that quantitative extraction occurs at pH 1-5. Above or below this pH the extraction was found to be incomplete. Obviously the pH range 1-5 was recommended for our routine work. Anions of buffers do not interfere on the extraction process as is seen from the effect of foreign ions.

Calibration Curve :

Different amounts of palladium were quantitatively extracted as described in the general procedure earlier at pH 4 and the optical densities of the chloroform extracts measured at 425 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. The aqueous phase in each case was clear and colorless. The results indicate that the system conforms Beer's law at this wave length over a concentration range of 1-10 μg Pd per ml.

Period of Extraction and Reagent Concentration :

Palladium is quantitatively extracted into chloroform in a single operation when the layers are shaken for 2 minutes and a 2 min period is just as sufficient as 10 or 20 min period.

Variation of reagent concentration was tested at pH 4, the other variables remaining the same. It has been found that 1 ml of 0.5% acetic solution of the reagent is sufficient to extract 188.8 μg Pd. Reagent concentration below 0.4% results incomplete extraction. Higher concentration ($>0.6\%$) was avoided because of reagent economy.

Molar Absorptivity and Sensitivity :

The molar absorptivity of the complex is calculated and found to be 6.644×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 425 nm (on the basis of palladium content) and sensitivity in terms of Sandell's definition is 0.015 μg .

Stability of the Colour :

The optical densities of the chloroform extract containing 188.8 μg Pd extracted as above were measured at different intervals of time showing that the colour of the complex is stable at least for 36 hours. At the end of 48 hours the absorbance decreases by about 3%. So it seems to be convenient to measure the optical densities within 36 hours after the extraction.

The stability constant of the chelate has been evaluated to be 2.457×10^6 which shows that the

complex is highly stable. The standard free energy of formation (ΔF°) of the complex is calculated and found to be -8.82 K cal/mole at 27°.

Interference :

In order to study the effect of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour palladium(II) was extracted and determined accordingly in presence of 25-fold excess of different cations. A preliminary study shows that platinum(IV), rhodium(III), nickel(II), chromium(III), uranium(VI), aluminium(III), beryllium(II), cerium(III), lead(II), thallium(III) do not interfere. Interference due to Co(II) may be avoided by a preliminary extraction with ammonium thiocyanate. Manganese(II), cadmium(II), mercury(II), zinc(II) form a light yellow precipitate with the reagent. All attempts to mask these cations in the aqueous phase were failed. In presence of copper(II) and iron(III) the chloroform extracts are deep brown and blackish ones and hamper the procedure. Presence of osmium(VIII) and ruthenium(III) inhibits the extraction process as it prohibits the formation of Pd(II) complex.

100-fold excess of the anions as mentioned is tolerable in the extraction process, e.g., citrate, acetate, borate, phthalate, tartrate, phosphate, sulfate, nitrate. EDTA, however, has an adverse effect.

Reproducibility :

Determination of different amount of palladium shows that the results are accurate to within $\pm 1.2\%$, thus rendering the process to be fairly precise and reproducible.

Preparation of Solid Chelate :

5 ml of PdCl₂ stock solution was diluted to about 25 ml with distilled water and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 4 by adding suitable amount of dilute hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide drop by drop. To this solution was added a sufficient excess of acetic solution of the reagent (1%, 5 ml) was added. A bright yellow coloured precipitate was immediately formed and was allowed to settle for 25 min. The precipitate was then filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible, washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) to remove any excess of the reagent. The chelate was then dried at $110 \pm 5^\circ$ to a constant weight as Pd(C₁₀H₈NO)₂.

Analysis of the Complex :

The analysis of the element in the complex was carried out by standard methods. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen were analysed by the Mikro-Analytische Laboratorium, West-Germany. Palladium was estimated gravimetrically as in the standardisation step after destroying the ligand by sulfuric acid, nitric acid and perchloric acid treatment.

Element	Analytical Data	
	Found %	Required for Pd(C ₁₀ H ₉ NO) ₂
C	57.1	56.9
H	3.6	3.7
N	6.5	6.6
Pd	25.2	25.1

Thermogravimetric Analysis of the Complex :

Thermogravimetric analysis of the precipitated complex (4.4 mg) in air (heating rate 5°/min) shows that decomposition starts at 270° before that traces of sublimation arises at 240-270°. The decomposition occurs in two steps indicating the decomposition of the two rings of the ligand in two steps. First ring decomposes between 270 to 300° while the second between 300 to 390°. Final residue was 1.1 mg.

TGA of the complex (7.4 mg) in flowing nitrogen atmosphere shows the decomposition of the complex at 175°. An weight loss (10%) within 130° is perhaps partly due to the loss of associated moisture and absorbed precipitant and partly due to volatilisation of the complex. No change in weight is found after 550°. Residue left was 2.2 mg.

TGA in flowing hydrogen shows that the complex (6.3 mg) decomposes at 155°. At 100° a 0.75% weight gain is perhaps due to hydrogen adsorption. Final residue was 1.6 mg. These have been illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. TGA of palladium complex in air (A), in nitrogen (B) and in Hydrogen (C).

The consequent studies shows that the stability of the complex in different atmosphere is in the following order :

Air or oxidising atmosphere > Nitrogen atmosphere > Hydrogen atmosphere

Differential Thermal Analysis of the Complex :

The DTA curve was recorded using a mixture of the complex and precalcined α -Al₂O₃. The diluant alpha (α -Al₂O₃) alumina was precalcined at 1300° several hours and finally powdered. This powder was used as a diluant of the complex for recording the DTA trace. An endotherm at 90° corresponds moisture. This is followed by a very small but sharp endothermic peak at 260°, which signifies the vapourisation of the complex in trace amount. The main decomposition commenced at 270° with a round-shaped exotherm. A break on the curve at 300° corresponds the half of the total weight lost in the case of TGA of the complex in air. Another break at 400° on the DTA curve can be observed. The TGA curve, however, does not show a further weight loss. Thus the degradation has been ceased at this temperature. Further continuation of the exotherm probably indicates an oxidation process of the residue, which has been ceased at 600°. This has been illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. DTA in air, heating rate 5°/min, chromel-alumel thermocouple, sargent mR recorder, sensitivity 5 mv.

Magnetic Properties :

Freshly prepared complex (12.7 mg) was taken in a bucket of a precision Faraday type magnetic balance, specific magnetic susceptibility at 25° was found to be -0.85×10^{-6} e.m.u. The balance was calibrated with A.R. sucrose before the measurement step. The precipitate is strongly diamagnetic in nature. TGA residue in air (black) as also diamagnetic in nature at 25°. This shows that it is not metallic palladium which is paramagnetic having a magnetic susceptibility of 5×10^{-6} e.m.u. at 20°.

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